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Pandemic Impacted into Shifting of Social Support Paradigm: A descriptive study in Nepal

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ABSTRACT

Local social support practices chain has disconnected due to higher practices on social distancing due to pandemic. Fear of contaminate, dominated state order, and continue of social distancing impacted into social support in local practices. The study has explored how resourceless household has been struggling on achieving social support in their community, how the micro level benefit receiver houses impacted into the local level, and how it has impacted due to local state regularities for social distances in high hill communities of Nepal. The research paper has explored existing local support practices and major hindering factors during the pandemic impacted communities in the study area. A descriptive research methodology has been used. Primary information has been collected from a close-ended questionnaire through local informants. Pandemic, social support, local support and community-based initiatives on self-support related to publication information have been considered as secondary sources of the study. Descriptive and inferential analysis has been used for quantitative data analysis. Local support is impacted due to limited movement, high restriction on social gathering, policy domination on transportation, networking, and labor engagement. It can be possible to enhance local support sustainability through the support during pandemic through the collective funds, assets, community-based policies, and local promotional policy on building community resilience.

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Pandemic, collectivism, social-capital, social-support, resilience

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BACKGROUND

Social support behaviors help to lessen current shocks and pressures, particularly during pandemics. Social safety nets can be defined as social support systems and social capital. Social

support interventions in this study can be classified as household capacity, community-based social capacity, external support elements, and legal support components. This may improve

a community's ability to recover, particularly when a pandemic will occur.

Social support strategies can reduce current and upcoming vulnerabilities. The official and informal social support systems can influence the effectiveness of a programmatic intervention. While informal safety nets offer the possibility of help to individuals to ensure they recover from shock and stress throughout pandemics, it can guarantee them access to economic or social support. The support that people might anticipate from their immediate and intermediate social networks in communities is referred to as social ensure the following and their provision. In order to generate assets for social assistance, people can work together, pool their resources, build up their assets, and save money for essentials while planning for pandemics.

Due to their limited capacity for coping and preparation, the poor and vulnerable may be more severely affected by a pandemic and suffer socioeconomic losses as a result. Along with this, due to the high alert of social distancing, and the scary ness of the spread of the virus due to social gatherings, most of the time the needy people and community have isolated from external support while they need social support.

A higher level of physical and social support can help overcome pandemic losses. By incorporating future sensitive preparedness, creating supporting networks, asset building, potential future readiness of coping plans of action, and institutional preparedness into targeted communities, concerned stakeholders

can boost the resilience capacity of impoverished and vulnerable communities. Following a disaster, local support systems can aid in social and economic recovery and give the affected community a chance to improve its situation through social protection from both public and private engagement.

For the needy population habitats, age groups, and ethnicities, social support is a crucial issue that might be contextual. Cumbera. M. G. et. al (2022) shared the worsened relationships with work colleagues, spouses, family, and friends also impacting the maximizing health-related issue, and it can be enhanced this quality of life through preservation of social engagement. Paitoonpong, S. et. al. (2008) has shared how social help practices have emerged greater prominently because the monetary crises in South Asia. Issues on social help practices, there's nonetheless sizable confusion amongst students and national, and worldwide businesses concerning the use and which means of the social help practices term. Social help may be described as helping protection nets, whilst groups be afflicted by outside threats and uncertainties. Especially, whilst network families are impacted with the aid of using outside shocks and getting strain into each day lives and livelihoods, social help can paintings for early restoration of their neighborhood pattern.

Social support is regularly assessed below 3 categories: perceived aid, aid behaviors (obtained aid), and aid resources. Studies of the negative effects of social relationships and of support-giving, mutual coping and support-giving

dynamics, optimal "matches" between people's needs and support received, and characteristics of groups that can offer a sense of social support are some of the promising new directions in social support research.

Thoits, P. A. (1985) briefly summarize the relatively little is known about the complications of stressors' impact on physical health outcomes compared to mental health outcomes, including differential physical vulnerability to stress by social position, to simply summarize with regard to the source of stressors. The author continued, "It is important to further examine the social determinants of various psychosocial resources as well as the interactions among psychological and social resources." A sense of control influences coping behaviour (and vice versa).

It may be most effective to study people's proactive attempts to cope with specific stressors to understand the complicated interplay between personal agency and systemic limitations on that agency. From a theoretical and empirical standpoint, additional research on flexibility as a successful coping mechanism could be beneficial. It is important to study the relationships between structural-functional aspects of social support, the distribution of perceived and received support, how support influences personality resources (and vice versa), how supportive assistance is mobilized versus eroded, and what types of support best meet people's assistance needs.

When pandemics spread through a community, it has a profoundly negative impact on the social,

economic, and social support contexts that influence human society, particularly impoverished homes. The demand for the study has recently changed from focusing on shocks and risk reduction, social protection, and social support activities separately to focusing on social support. While most researchers have assumed that lower-status, disadvantaged groups experience more unpleasant situations and continuing stress in their lives, the evidence only supports the inverse distribution of ongoing stress by social status.

Disadvantaged groups are not always more susceptible to stress, though. Different groups appear to be prone to different subsets of stressors when cumulative indices of events or strains are broken down into specific sorts of stressors. In particular, women appear to be more susceptible to "network events" whereas men might be more susceptible to pressures related to money and the workplace. It is not always the case that people with lower status face more unfavourable incidents. The association between social status and life changes frequently depends on the events that are included in a study's analysis (e.g., whether events that could happen to one's friends or family are included). In general, persons with more social roles run a higher chance of experiencing more network events and personal losses than those with less roles. Despite variations in the association between social status and exposure to negative situations, research on stress shows that those who belong to disadvantaged social groups are more likely to become emotionally reactive or vulnerable to stressors. Women, the elderly, single people, and

people with lower socioeconomic status show higher socioeconomic distress or depression ratings than their counterparts with higher socioeconomic status when compared at equal levels or intensities of stress experience. (Chongbang, 2021).

A systematic study on pandemics and how its impacted into social support practices in community-driven intervention, how the local social support practices has impacted are still lacking. This paper will try to find how the pandemic has impacted into local support practices provision due to social distancing, local policies and personal fear to mass transmission. This study will explore how local people were keeping distancing among in communities, how it has impacted on deliver social support to needy people, and what are the major lesson learned from this pandemic.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical

Especially, this paper is based on the testing of collectivism and social support theory. The major concern of this study is how the pandemic impacted community collectivism on social support to needy people during the emergency. Spicker, (2022) shared how collectivism is a set of ideas, principles, and approaches that begin from the recognition of the collective aspects of social life. Where individualism views actions, decisions, and policies from the perspective of independent, single actors, collectivism focuses on social groups, communities, and the wider society. Spicker has further builds arguments based on a distinctive analytical framework,

outlining a framework that outlines three discrete separate approaches to individualism: moral, methodological, methodical, and substantive (practical). Substantive Substantial individualism is based on the belief that all actions are the actions of individuals, individuals and that every social or political action is taken performed by individual human beings. individuals. Methodological individualism reviews examine economic, social, and political arguments as if they were based on the decisions of people one by one; individuals; the actions of groups are understood as a whole series of individual actions, added actions that are put together. Methodological individualism has argued with some force, but whether it applies depends on the circumstances; sometimes it works, and sometimes it doesn't. The most compelling arguments for individualism are moral. As a moral position, individualism is built on the defense of each individual: individuals have rights, and each person counts. There are crucial arguments for emphasizing the role of individualism in protecting the individual dignity, rights, and worth of every human being.

When considering collectivism, on the other hand, the strongest arguments for a collective approach are substantive. Substantial collectivism is the idea that we do not live as individuals but as members of social groups such as families, neighborhoods, and communities, and that many of our actions are performed collectively with others in organizations such as schools and businesses, and social institutions. People are what they are and who they are because they live and have relationships with

other people. Families, households, communities, organizations, and nations can all be treated as social units that have interests, concerns, and priorities that may differ from those of the individuals who make them up. Methodological collectivism looks for explanations and patterns of behavior not in the actions of individuals but in the actions of groups, including classes, ethnic groups, and societies. How the social units been activated during this pandemic and what are the main challenges and the way forward for the collective support of needy households and communities are questions extensively researched in this study paper.

Empirical

Social support may draw on people in need while dealing with life challenges and stressors are typically conceptualized in social support theory (Thoits, 1995 as cited in Lisa Kort-Butler, 2018). Cullen, Wright, and Chamlin (1999) as cited in Lisa Kort-Butler (2018) have extended this concept by defining social support as a process of transfer of human, cultural, material, and social capital, whether between individuals or between larger social units (communities, states) and their members. Support is generally provided informally through social interactions, but may also be formally assigned by an organization with official statuses, such as government aid programs or the legal system. Social support has both direct and indirect effects on crime and other well-being markers. As a result, people who receive social support are less likely to make mistakes. Social support can indirectly serve as a buffer between risk factors for crime and participation in criminal activity.

Initial support can be defined as perceived, feeling supported, or believing support is available, as opposed to receiving, reporting support was complete. Second, the support can be instrumental, informational, or emotional. Instrumental support is the provision of resources or assistance with practical activities or concerns, e.g. g. lending money or renting assets. Advice, guidance, or the provision of knowledge that can help an individual solve a problem, or carrier mentoring is known as informational support. Expressions of sympathy, caring, respect, appreciation, or encouragement constitute emotional support. Third, the source of social support can be distinguished. Members of a person's primary group, such as family members and friends, are often viewed as sources of support. Individuals may also seek support from secondary groups, such as schools, local groups, religious institutions, and local governmental agencies, where interactions are more regulated or hierarchical and less personal. The main sources of support, the level of support in a relationship, and the impact of support on behavior change throughout a person's life. (Umberson, Crosnoe, and Reczek, 2010 as cited in Lisa Kort-Butler 2018).

In recent decades, social support has become a crucial concept in development, including governmental and even community development perspectives. Several governments, development partners and local authorities have worked to enable social support through various forms of intervention. For example, say policies, programs, plans, and interventions. Those attempting to protect, risk mitigation, risk

transfer, enable capacity and facilitate recovery from various shocks and stresses, particularly in poor, vulnerable and affected communities. According of J.B. Asquith (2001): East Asia experienced a severe financial crisis in 1997 that led to negative growth in Indonesia, the Republic of Korea, Malaysia, the Philippines and Thailand and reversed decades of poverty reduction progress. As a result, the Asian Development Bank (ADB) and other international financial institutions provided emergency loans to protect social sector spending and expand safety nets. During this period, ADB funding for social protection increased from 1% to 2% to 13% of total funding, prompting the ADB to embark on a three-year process to develop its first social protection strategy. Srawoodh Paitoonpong (2008) explains that social support practices have come to the fore since the financial crisis. She goes on to explain social and local support practices such as the major Asian financial crises. She further explained; The safety net analogy comes from tightrope walkers who can be protected if they fall. Social support practices can be defined as social protection that can specifically facilitate private and public support mechanisms for the needy and vulnerable community while the shocks and stresses occur.

The social support practices can be executed multi-purpose, it should be more flexible and adaptable tools that the policymakers could use to improve the community resilience to cope with various future shocks and community stresses. Azize, H.T.A., & Gamil, R.E., (2020) discuss that social supportive practices have become key tools for policymakers. Writers have been educated on

the social support and protection programs that are implemented to achieve multiple goals such as reducing poverty and hunger and increasing the resilience of poor and vulnerable groups to various shocks. Recently, with the rapid spread of the COVID-19 pandemic, many countries started implementing social protection programs, and social support practices helped eliminate the negative impact of the COVID-19 pandemic crisis and improve community resilience. Larissa Pelham (2011) compares the case of why social support is an important tool for risk management in emergencies. The use of social support is advocated by both ex-ante (pre) to prevent and mitigate the impact of disasters and ex-post (post) to manage the impact of natural disasters. First, these papers examine the implications of contextual factors that must be considered when designing an effective social support system to respond to the needs generated by natural disasters.

It is very difficult to define any social support practice that can be earned as a proactive measure that could reduce the existing and future risks in the vulnerable community in its socio-economic recovery. It's hard to define a strong link between social support practices and community resilience, especially after an emergency. The poor and vulnerable are more vulnerable compared to socio-economically healthy communities. Daniel Longhurst (2020) explains the two main frameworks that guide work in the social support domain. First, the Adaptive Social Supportive Protection (ASP) framework examines how links between shocks, stresses, and linkage of social support can reduce the impact of

shocks and stressors on people's livelihoods and build resilience. Longhurst further compares the concept of Shock-Responsive Social Protection (SRSP) and provides a framework and typology to think about the different ways such as assessing climate vulnerability (CVA) and social protection (SP) through the horizontal and vertical categories can be linked extension, piggyback, alignment and design tweaks. In this paper, to try to move to program forward and identify gaps and risks, we move away from categories and look at how the frameworks have been applied operationally in different contexts. In this paper, the author raises the debate on linking Climate Vulnerability Assessment (CVA) and Social Protection (SP) as part of the broader and longstanding discussion of ways to link relief and development. A key problem with this long debate is that it tends to assume that stronger links between different parties are both right and achievable, provided the right concept and technical solutions can be developed. But if this is the case, then the literature largely fails to explain why this has been so difficult in practice and tends to overlook the fundamental difference.

A key issue in this long debate has been the gap between social support practices, social protection, and pandemic management. The community affected by the pandemic (Covid019) can be resilient if the anticipated risk mitigation measures have been deployed as a crisis management tool. But in this case, the extensive literature does not explain how social support initiatives and social protection packages were used as anticipation tools or risk reduction tools during the pandemic in the study area. Social

support can be defined as anticipating actions that can contribute to future risk reduction and help restore better capacity to the community affected by the pandemic. Wickramasinghe (2013) compares the significant impact of the disaster on poor and rich households in her study *Interrelation of Social Support in Sri Lanka on Disaster Management via Programs and Policies*. The author describes that Sri Lanka has experienced a remarkable increase in both the frequency and intensity of natural disasters in recent decades. Natural disasters have caused human, physical, financial, and environmental losses and have had a significant impact on Sri Lanka's economy. She added that the impact of natural disasters is not uniform across different parts of society. She has unearthed the distribution of disaster impacts depending on a region's degree of physical vulnerability to natural disasters and socioeconomic vulnerability. She added that the current system of social protection and social support initiatives in Sri Lanka does not adequately protect against vulnerability caused by natural disasters. The scope of current social protection programs is very limited, and the current system does not adequately address the real needs of disaster-prone group.

Bonding, bridging, and social support activities are important social assets during emergency management (Chongbang, 2021). The role of social support interventions can be to enhance people's abilities to use their connections and resources, which could be positive social capital as a survival mechanism for vulnerable communities. Rapeli (2017), compares how

Finnish social work practices are primed to develop future interventions and the use of social capital in emergency management. Their further analysis is based on the concept of social support initiatives and their forms of attachment, bridging, and linking. Results show that micro-level social work and tying up social support capital in emergency management stressed capacity. Bridging and linking the work of social support initiatives with disaster-related structures should be developed, and social support should improve pre- and post-emergency response capacities. She added that the concept of social capital was used in this study to represent valuable social networks between individuals, groups, or organizations that take the form of bonding, bridging, and linking.

The intervention of the social support initiatives can be highlighted based on the forecasting and post-reaction capacity of the state authorities and existing other development organizations. Sometimes policies and programs, and in some situations, responsiveness during recovery can make a difference. The money transfer system, savings capacity, livelihood support capacity, response, livelihood rescue capacity, and long-term livelihood support are important examples of local and social support in communities. SANN VATHANA et. Al. (2013) explain the natural disaster scenario in Cambodia by comparing the consequences of floods and droughts. This paper presents the impact of disasters on household well-being and the linkage effect of community and state social support interventions and shows how the failure to reach the rights of the poor and vulnerable through the

impacts of floods and droughts has been. This study strongly emphasized the formulation of a strong policy design for social support interventions to emphasize ex-ante tools (forecast) rather than ex-post response (post) to disasters, given the emphasis on emergency response and relief. Nopphol, W. (2015) elicits examines the relationships between social support and action to reduce disaster risk from the 2021 Indian tsunami. The authors unearth participation in communications and obtained an early warning system and an application to daily behaviors relevant to reducing the disaster risk contributes. The local practice of disaster risk reduction measures, improving forecasts.

RESEARCH GAP

Community-based social support practices, and preparedness planning are still lacking aligned with pandemic response due to lower level of capacity and preparedness (Chongbang, 2021). The existing social support practices were quite silent in interlinking with pandemic preparedness. Where the existing policy and planning process still has seemed gap between bounce back better capacity of communities with the social support of local intervention in the targeted area. The micro-level social support and bridging with social capital in communities still seem to gap. This study's results can contribute to finding out how social support practices could contribute to building a resilient capacity of community during the pandemic in the study area, especially in condition of Covid019 and similar pandemics.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Despite the great number multitude of recent studies on the nature and consequences of social support, the present current state of knowledge in this area only allows only the general conclusion that it somehow promotes in some way enhances the social, economic, mental, mental, and physical capacity. What it is, how it is provided and by whom, whom it is provided, and how and under what conditions it affects social capacity, and performance are open questions. It is argued that it is the fallacious assumption of a single commodity social support which lies at that underlies the root of the present current confusion

and that a multi-dimensional conceptual frame of reference frame is a necessity for further advancement advances in the field and the development of effective assessment and intervention strategies. Such a differentiated framework is developed and shown to be consistent with the present current state of empirical and theoretical knowledge. This framework is applied to the conceptual analysis of social support measures used in some frequent collection of filed responses, interlinked with empirical research on social support, cited with well-cited empirical studies and inline following empirical thoughts, reasoning whose discrepant contradictory results are shown to derive arise from differences in the study area.

Figure 1: Social Support Practices.

METHOD

The study approaches the test objectives by examining the relationships between variables. The methodology examines the relationship between existing social support practices and the impact of the Covid019 pandemic in the study area, which was significant. The study examines the Anthropocene understanding of cause and effect between social support practices and the impact of pandemic (Covid019)-affected households. Social support is collective action in communities to respond collectively. Through team commitment, collective policies, and plans, providing collective support to needy households

during a pandemic can be defined as social support in the study area. The study is based on either single or multiple realities. What is the local support, how have the informal institutions been supported, what are the main support policies at the local level, how did the needy population identify themselves, what is the condition for positive discrimination and who is mainly responsible for social support initiatives? worry about learning.

This study required qualitative and quantitative data for descriptive and exploratory research. Both primary and secondary data were collected. Primary data will analyze the cause and effect of

social support and its impact on local capacities in response to the Covid019 pandemic. Descriptive interpretation based on information gathered that will be contextual, real-world-based knowledge of the social support initiatives and their impact on the resilience of households that have suffered from disasters.

Due to the limited number of researchers in this field, a non-probable convenience sample was used. Most of the data collectors were from Nawalparasi, Mustang, and Lamjung districts in Gandaki province, Nepal. Most of the informants are from the local leading agency for on-site pandemic response with coordination of the Local Coordination and Management Committee of Covid019 (LCMC) in the affected area. Due to limited human resources, the study was organized by selected respondents from different communities, particularly those from Higher (Nawalparasi), Middle (Lamjung), and Lower (Mustang) districts. Closed-ended questions were formulated, shared with local data collectors via local representatives, and collected from direct answers. It took almost ten days to two months to collect responses from the field, and around 72 representatives responded to this study. The data are analyzed in a descriptive analysis based on 72 respondents in qualitative data mostly analyzed from survey data and interviews and multiple regression was analyzed based on 72 respondents in quantitative data to complete the study results.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Local institutional support:

The mean value is 0.5 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 1 (Yes) and some of have 0 (No). Mode value is 1 (Yes) which is significantly respond is yes. Standard error reflecting only 0.05. Standard deviation is 0.50 and sample variance is 0.25. The total sum of responses is 36 and total respondents are 72. Most of the respondents said the local institutional support is crucial on social support but hardly the get response during the pandemic due to lower local institutional preparedness in local informal setup.

Cash Based Preparedness:

The mean value is 0.23 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 0 (no) and some of have 1 (Yes). Mode value is 0 (Nes) which is significantly respond is 'No'. Standard error reflecting only 0.051. Standard deviation is 0.429 and sample variance is 0.184. 23.61% respondents said they have experiences on cash-based preparedness on social support.

is significantly respond is ‘Not having much government policy preparedness’. Standard error reflecting only 0.055, standard deviation is 0.469 and sample variance is 0.220. Total 31.94% respondents said they have experiences on government policy preparedness on social support locally.

Informal support institutions:

The mean value is 0.34 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 0 (No) and some of have 1 (Yes). Mode value is 0 (No) which is significantly respond is ‘No’. Standard error reflecting only 0.056 Standard deviation is 0.479 and sample variance is 0.229. Total 34.72% respondents said they have experiences on informal support institutions on social support.

Virtual support preparedness:

The mean value is 0.097 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 1 (Yes) and some of have 0 (No). Mode value is 0 (No) which is significantly respond is ‘Not having much virtual support preparedness’. Standard error reflecting only 0.035, standard deviation is 0.02989 and sample variance is 0.089. Total 9.72% respondents said they have experiences on virtually support preparedness for social support locally.

Government policy preparedness:

The mean value is 0.319 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 1 (Yes) and some of have 0 (No). Mode value is 0 (No) which

Immediate response team:

The mean value is 0.555 in respondents, maximum value of respondents is 1 (Yes) and some of have 0 (No). Mode value is 1 (Yes) which is significantly respond is yes. Standard error reflecting only 0.0271. Standard deviation is 0.230 and sample variance is 0.053. The total sum of responses is 4 and total respondents are 72. Most of the respondents said the immediate response team has in lower level in local level for pandemic responding setup.

Status of Immediate response team in local level

- Immediate response team
- Not having of response team

INFERENTIAL ANALYSIS

SUMMARY OUTPUT

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	1
R Square	1
Adjusted R Square	1
Standard Error	3.26E-16
Observations	72

<i>ANOVA</i>		<i>Significance</i>						
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>F</i>			
Regression	6	84	14	1.3146	0			
Residual	65	0	0					
Total	71	84						

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	9.7E-17	6.9E-17	1.4E+00	0.162	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Local institutions support	1	7.842E-17	1.2752E+16	0	1	1	1	1
Cash based preparedness	1	9.410E-17	1.06274E+16	0	1	1	1	1
Informal support institutions	1	8.134E-17	1.22942E+16	0	1	1	1	1
Government policy preparedness	1	8.277E-17	1.20819E+16	0	1	1	1	1
Virtual support preparedness	1	1.335E-16	7.49049E+15	0	1	1	1	1
Immediate response team	1	1.720E-16	5.81497E+15	0	1	1	1	1

The coefficient seems strong (nearly 1) which seems the positive relation between (Social support capacity and supporting initiatives (Local institutions support, Cash based preparedness, Informal support institutions, Government policy preparedness, Virtual support preparedness, and

Immediate response team). The F statistics seem significant for the entire regression. At a (alpha) is below value than 0.05, this regression is statistically significant because 'P-value is < 0.05. All five T values are not statistically significant, because their corresponding P-value is above (>

0.05. Therefore, all six; X1 (Local institutions support), X2 (Cash based preparedness), X3 (Informal support institutions), X4 (Government policy preparedness), and X5 (Virtual support preparedness), X6 (and Immediate response team) are individually in the prediction of Y (Social support building). Therefore, the prediction equation Y:

$$= \text{Intercept} + B1*(X1) + B2*(X2) + B3*(X3) + B4*(X4) + B5*(X5)$$

$$= 9.7* + B18*1 + 1*1 + 0*1 + 0*1 + 0*1 + 0$$

$$= 10.7$$

Significantly, through the Local institutions support, Cash based preparedness, Informal support institutions, Government policy preparedness, Virtual support preparedness, and Immediate response team during the pandemic, every household could scale up their social support capacity by 10.7%.

The main concern of this study is how community collectivism is being carried out during the pandemic, particularly in providing social support to those in need. Due to the lack of structures at community and local level, social support seems quite weak and needs to strengthen their capacity for further response planning. Due to the higher social distancing warnings, the higher spread of the Covid019 virus and lower preparedness at the local level, collectivism in a community is not at a satisfactory level. Social groups such as families, neighborhoods and communities are trying to come together, but due to fears of virus infection and restrictions on social gatherings by concerned authorities, there

is not collective support as expected. Families, households, communities and local organizations can be treated as social units that have interests, concerns and priorities that can contribute to the collective during the pandemic, reflected as collectivist behavior of actions in groups, including classes, ethnic groups and societies. But due to the high social distances, there is not the expected collective support during the pandemic.

Rapeli (2017) compares how Finnish social work practices are prepared to develop future interventions and the use of social capital in emergency management. But when the health emergency hits, as with Covid019, social work has not worked as predicted. Need for preparation as a collective action with a full readiness phase to conceptualize social support initiatives and their forms of attachment, bridging, and linking. In her study Interrelation of social support in Disaster Management, Wickramasinghe (2013) compares the significant impact of the disaster on poor and rich households. But the pandemic is hitting poorer households harder than wealthy ones due to their lower savings status, and lacking immediate support from external support mechanisms due to restrictions on social gatherings. Chongbang (2021) improves bonding, bridging, and linking social support activities, but while the pandemic is occurring in the community, social distancing is breaking the chain of community bonding and those in need and the household have had a greater impact compared to others. Bonding, bridging, and social support activities are important social

assets during emergency management (Chongbang, 2021).

CONCLUSION

Better preparation of local institutions support, cash-based preparedness, informal support institutions, government policy preparedness, virtual support preparedness, and immediate response team can contribute into building of social support locally.

Author Note

Mr. Chongbang © <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8164> is a Ph.D. candidate at Tribhuvan University in Nepal. Highly interested in research, paper writing, and publication via knowledge building. Already published some papers from Bangladesh, India, Pakistan, Nigeria, Indonesia, Vietnam, and Nepal.

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Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Disclosure statement

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